

METHODS USED IN DIGESTIBILITY EVALUATION OF FISH DIETS: A REVIEW AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt at taking a critical look at work done on digestibility studies in fish nutrition research. It also made an assessment of the various inert markers used in digestibility studies both external and internal (indigenous). It observed that although chromic oxide is the most widely used external marker prospect exist for the use of indigenous markers like crude fibre and acid insoluble ash, that are part of the diet or nutrient in the feed. It also looked at the components of these inert markers. Furthermore, the methods used in faecal collection were x-rayed and this includes faecal collection from the rearing tank, from the lower part of the large intestine and from metabolism chambers. The demerits in each of these methods were highlighted. Finally, the inherent challenges in the course of carrying out research work on digestibility were evaluated and suggestions and recommendations made on how to overcome some of these challenges.

KEY WORDS: Digestibility, internal and indigenous markers, faecal collection, methodology.

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INTRODUCTION

Very few nutrients are utilized by an animal in the form in which they are ingested. Digestion processes must split amino acids from protein molecules, complex carbohydrates must be broken down to simple sugars and fats must be hydrolyzed to fatty acids, monoglycerides and di-glycerides before the nutrients can be absorbed. The nutritive value of a feed is dependent not only upon the nutrient content, but also upon the ability of an animal to digest and absorb the nutrients in the feed. This ability varies greatly with the type of animal and the feed material. Digestion is the process by which ingested materials are reduced to molecules of small enough size or other appropriate characteristics for absorption i.e. passage through the gut wall into the blood stream. This generally means that proteins are hydrolyzed to amino acids or to polypeptide chains of a few amino acids, digestible carbohydrates to simple sugars, and lipids to fatty acids and glycerol. Materials not absorbed are by definition indigestible and are eventually voided as faeces. Digestibility is a measure of the nutritional usefulness of food. In order words, it is the degree to which a food or its nutrient components are made absorbable by an organism.

One of the most important aspects in the evaluation of the biological effectiveness of a foodstuff is the determination of its digestibility. This measure the ability of the fish to digest and absorb the nutrients it is fed. Studies on digestibility in fish commenced as a sequel to the development and dependence on artificial diets as aquaculture intensifies.

Modern aquaculture diets are complex assemblages of a range of raw materials processed to make a feed that satisfies the demands of the animal for nutrients and energy. In most modern fish diets, the specifications are now often prescribed on a digestible nutrient and energy basis. In the formulation process not only are the diet specifications critical aspect to the diet but also the cost of the formulation, its processability (ability to make it

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into a pellet) and also the consideration of the potential for certain raw materials to introduce deleterious biologically active compounds are all important issues. The food value of any food is an important item when its usefulness as a food is taken into account, but of equal importance is the manner in which the body uses the food, that is, whether it digests the food with ease or with difficulty. Therefore, when the value of food for fish is to be determined, its digestibility must receive definite consideration.

This paper does not claim to be a comprehensive review on fish digestibility, but is an attempt to cover relevant aspect such as inert reference compounds used as markers; methods used in the collection of metabolic wastes, and the challenges faced in digestibility research studies. (Leavitt 1985; Lin et al. 2004, Glencross 2005 Sotolu and Faturoti; 2008; Hussain et al. 2011; Bob-Manuel and Erondu 2011.

THE USE OF MARKERS IN DIGESTIBILITY STUDIES

The quantitative collection of faecal material and maintenance of quantitative records of feed intake is avoided with the use of indicator substances or markers. Markers were originally utilized for domestic animals by Edin (1918) who used chromic oxide (Cr_2O_3) was proposed as an inert reference compound in digestibility determination for livestock. Since then this indicator has been in common use for studies in fish digestibility (Windell and Bowen 1978; Smith *et al.*, 1980, Horico-Querijero and Chiu 1989; Lovel 1994; Fenerci and Sener 2005; Gul *et al.* 2007; Sotolu and Faturoti 2008).

Markers could also be of two forms:

1. Artificial foreign substances (Table I) introduced into the feed in small quantities (external markers).
2. Substances that are a component of the feed itself (internal markers) In either case, the markers have to conform to four basic criteria which include
 - i. They should not interfere with the digestive metabolism of the animal
 - ii. Should not be absorbed through the lumen,
 - iii. Should not move along the gut at a differential velocity from the rest of the food material, and
 - iv. Should not be toxic.

Table 1. Different types of internal (indigenous) and external markers used in digestibility studies.

Markers
Internal
Hydrolysis Resistant Ash (HRA) or
Acid insoluble Ash (AIA)
Hydrolysis Resistant Organic Matter (HROM)
Crude Fibre (CF)
Ash
Cellulose
Silica
External
Chromic Oxide (Cr_2O_3)
^{32}P (insoluble Ammonium molybdate)
Titanium IV Oxide
Celite (as a supplementation to AIA)
Polythene
Magnesium ferrite ($MgOFe_2O_3$)

Source: Modified from De Silva (1989)

Even though Cr_2O_3 is widely used and continues to be as an external marker, Bowen (1978) observed in *Tilapia mossambica* that Cr_2O_3 moved at a different rate than the rest of the food. Hilton *et al* (1981) found that

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extruded-pelleted feed moved slower than steam-pelleted feed due to the lower density of the latter. De Silva and Owoyemi (1983) reported that the specific gravity of the diet affects its rate of passage through the gut. The above observations raise some doubt regarding the use of external markers. This point out to the need of more extensive controlled experiments to determine and evaluate the degree of accuracy in digestibility estimates obtained using external markers as against the use of internal markers and the direct method.

The need therefore arises to identify other dietary markers, which may be more suitable under practical farming conditions where it is not always possible to introduce a 'foreign' dietary marker. Earlier work with fish have shown that cellulose (Buddington 1979) hydrolysis resistant organic matter (HROM: Buddington 1980; De Silva and Perera 1983), crude fibre (Tacon and Rodrigues 1984; Bob-Manuel and Erundu 2011; De Silva and Perera 1983) and hydrolysis resistant ash (Bowen, 1981; De Silva and Perera 1983; Sadiku *et al* 2001) may offer particular promises as natural (indigenous) markers for estimating nutrient digestibility.

Table 2. Main Components of Internal markers used in digestibility studies

Marker	Component
CF	Cellulose and lignin fractions
HROM	Cellulose, chitin
HRA (=AIA)	Minerals, ash resistant to acid digestion; primary silica

Source: De Silva (1989)

In essence there is still a controversy as to whether internal or external indicators are more suitable and or reliable and which specific ones are to be used in digestibility estimations in fish. The balance of evidence tends to indicate that indigenous markers, which are found in appreciable quantity in the diet, are more suitable than external markers. (De Silva 1989). For example, when using AIA as a marker Thonney *et al.* (1984) recommends that it is desirable that the diet contains AIA in excess of 0.75%. Utilization of an internal and or an indigenous maker also eliminates and additional step of mixing the marker into the diet.

Among the internal markers (Table 2) that are generally used in digestibility estimations, CF has been shown to be assimilated to a very small extent at least by certain species (Niederholzer and Hofer 1979; Van Dyke and Sulton 1977) and similarly even a small fraction of HROM from the detrital aggregate of *Tilapia mossambica* (Bowen 1981) Thonney (1981) demonstrated the deliberate addition to supplement an endogenous marker, in this case a supplement of HRA (or Acid Insoluble Ash – AIA) increased the precision of the measurements. These observations were endorsed by Atkinson *et al.* (1984) who used celite to supplement HRA in their practical diets for rainbow trout. De Silva and Perera (1983) compared the validity of HROM, HRA and CF as markers based on experiments with the *Asian ciclilid*, *Etroplus suratensis* (Bloch) fed aquatic weed, Hydrilla and concluded the HROM was the most appropriate on the basis of the degree of precision that could be achieved in quantification.

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Experimental Procedure

The steps involved in estimating the digestibility of a diet and its nutrient components could be presented in a flow diagram as follows.

Source: Cho *et al* (1985)

MEASUREMENT OF DIGESTIBILITY

Chromium oxide (Cr_2O_3) mixed with prepared diets and measured in the faeces provides a general comparison of the overall digestibility of a feed expressed as:

$$\text{Percent digestibility} = 100 - \frac{\% \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \text{ in faeces}}{\% \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \text{ in feed}}$$

More Specific measurements of digestibility now seem to be replacing the use of Cr_2O_3 as an indicator. Measurements of the caloric values of ingested food and faeces produced provides some part of the information for estimating the energy balance for fish (oxygen consumption and growth rate are also needed). Alternatively,

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protein (measured as nitrogen content) or lipid content of food and faeces could be measured. In both cases the equation would be;

$$\text{Percent digestibility} = \frac{\text{Nutrient intake} - \text{nutrient in faeces}}{\text{Nutrient intake}} \times 100$$

In measuring protein nitrogen, one really should take the nitrogen from the deaminated amino acids into account, which requires measuring the ammonia excreted by the gills (metabolic nitrogen). The equation should be:

$$\text{Percent digestibility} = \frac{\text{Intake N} - (\text{faecal N} - \text{metabolic N})}{\text{intake N}} \times 100$$

Some of the most extensive studies on the digestibility of food components have been performed and reported by Phillips (1969) and readers should see these for detailed methods.

Several authors have combined the use of an indicator or other general measurement with measurement of one food component, generally protein. As an example, Smith and Lovell (1973) combined measurement of protein nitrogen with Cr₂O₃. Their equation was:

$$\% \text{Digestibility} = 100 - \frac{\% \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \text{ in feed} \times \% \text{ protein in faeces}}{\% \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \text{ in faeces} \times \% \text{ protein in feed}}$$

The apparent crude protein digestibility coefficients of Pacu, *Piaractusbrachypomus* was determined, Fernandes *et al* (2004), for Soybean meal (SBM), Fishmeal (F.M.), corn (CN) and Wheat bran (WB). The results were 75.88, 90.49, 85.06, and 61.62% respectively.

The apparent digestibility coefficient (ADC) of dry matter, crude protein, lipid, gross energy, amino acids and fatty acids in white fishmeal, brown fish meal, soybean meal, peanut meal and yeast were determined Lin *et al* (2004), for grouper *Epinephelus coloides*. Apparent protein 80.79 ± 1.95 and 61.14 ± 0.54% for white fish meal, brown fish meal, soybean meal, peanut meal and yeast respectively. White fishmeal and brown fishmeal showed higher protein digestibility among ingredients tested (P<0.01).

The digestibility by tilapia of some dietary protein sources is presented in Table 3. The apparent digestibility coefficients of ingredients measured with rainbow trout is also presented in table 4.

Table 3. Digestibility by tilapia of some dietary protein sources

Source	1 ^a	2 ^b	3 ^a	4 ^a	5 ^a	6 ^a	7 ^c	8 ^a
Fishmeal	92.22	85	72	86	92	64		
Fish silage								
Meat and bone meal	92.2	68-78						
Poultry offal meal				74				
Shrimp meal					87		74	
Silkworm pupa meal		91.1						
Brewers grains			63				63	
Azolla					75			
Casein					97.2			
Copra meal					36	81		
Corn gluton meal	90.7				97			
Cottonseed meal			31				90	
Cottonseed cake						90		
Groundnut meal			79					
Soybean meal		90.9	94		91	93	91	94.4
Full-fat toasted soybean							90	

1 Watanabe *et al* (1996), 2 Popma (1982). 3 Luquet (1989), 4 Hanley (1987).

5 Lorico-Ouerijero and Chiu (1989). 6 Moreau (1996), 7 Degani *et al.* (1997).

And 8 Fountainhas-Fernandes *et al.* (1999); a = *Nile tilapia*, b= *O. auteus* and C= *aureus* x *O. niloticus*.

Table 4. Apparent digestibility coefficients of ingredients measured with rainbow trout

Ingredients	Apparent digestibility Coefficients (%)			
	Dry Matter	Crude Protein	Lipid	Energy
Alfalfa	39	87	71	43
Blood meal	87	85	-	-
Ring-dried	91	96	-	92
Spray-dried	55	16	-	50
Flame-dried	76	91	-	77
Corn Yellow	23	95	-	39
Corn gluten feed	23	92	-	29
Corn gluten meal	80	96	-	83
Corn distiller dried Soluble	46	85	71	51
Feather meal	77	77	-	77
Fish meal, herring	85	92	97	91
Meat and bone Meal	70	85	-	80
Poultry by-products Meal	76	89	-	82
Rapeseed meal	35	77	-	45
Soybean meal Dehulled	74	96	-	75
Wheat middlings	35	92	-	46
Whey, dehydrated	97	96	-	94
Fish protein Concentrate	90	95	-	94
Soy protein Concentrate	77	97	-	84

Source: (Cho *et al.* 1982; Cho and kaushik, 1990).

METHODS OF COLLECTING METABOLIC WASTES FROM FISH

Digestibility of diets, and by inference certain components raw materials are one of the more practical assessment methods used in aquaculture nutrition research. There are ranges of methods that can be used to determine the digestibility of raw materials and the key considerations include the diets design and faecal collection method used (Glencross *et al.*, 2005). There has been considerable debate over the more relevant method to use in the collection of faeces for the assessment of digestibility in fish. The separation and recovery of waste products from the aquarium water is the most difficult part of the digestibility determination in fish. Several methods have been used to accomplish this.

Removal of faeces from aquarium water

Mechanical removal of solids from the aquarium water is probably the most widely used method for obtaining faecal material. (Schneider *et al.*, 2004, Fenerci and Sener 2005, Gul *et al.* 2007; Sotolu and Faturoti 2008) Soon after the fish are fed, the aquarium is flushed to remove any uneaten food. Alternatively the fish can be fed in one aquarium and transferred in a net to another aquarium for faecal collection. Faecal collection is usually done in an aerated aquarium without water change. It is erroneously assumed that faecal matter is insoluble and soluble material is urine or gill excretions unfortunately, soluble excretions are lost.

Mechanical methods for collection of faeces ranges from simply removing the faecal pellets periodically with a fine mesh net to elaborate mechanical dives centrifugation and filtration of aquarium water have also been used. Obviously it is impossible to get quantitative collection of faeces by netting or centrifugation.

Usually, an indigestible marker chromic oxide is used, and digestibility is calculated by the ratio of nutrient to marker in feed and faeces (Smith and Lovell 1973; Lovell 1994). An evaluation was made on the gravimetric and inert marker techniques in digestibility studies (Leavitt 1985; Noue and Choubert 1986), and concluded that

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reliable digestibility estimates could be obtained by the direct method (total collection of faeces) with an automatic fish faeces collector. Both methods pose the common difficulty of obtaining a collection of a representative faecal sample.

The techniques which involve the periodic collection of faeces by siphoning from the bottom of a tank are also likely to yield inaccurate estimates of digestibility since the break up of faecal materials by fish movement may lead to leaching of nutrients and therefore, overestimation of digestibility of nutrients. There are three methods or systems that are acclaimed to produce meaningful estimates of digestibility of nutrients if used correctly. The system of Ogino *et al* (1973) in which the faeces are collected by passing the effluent water from the fish tanks through a filtration column (TUF Column), Cho *et al* (1985) in which a settling column is used to separate the faeces from the effluent water (Guelph system) and Choubert *et al.* (1979) in which a mechanically rotating-screen is used to filter out faecal material (St. Pee system). These three systems have been adopted in several laboratories around the world. These two systems apparently yield very similar apparent digestibility coefficients. In a study comparing the TUF column and the Guelph system, very similar ADC of dry matter, protein, lipid and energy were obtained with both methods for two reference diet (Sato *et al.*, 1992).

Removal of faeces from lower large intestines (rectum).

Several investigators have collected the contents of the lower large intestine before it is naturally expelled by the fish. Windel and Bowen 1978; Smith *et al* 1980; Horico Querijero and Chiu 1989, Balogun *et al* 2004

When using a marker to estimate digestibility only a small faecal sample is needed, but this sample must represent quantitatively the undigested portion of the feed and be uncontaminated with slime, urine, or sexual products. Samples have been obtained by external pressure and by sacrificing the fish and dissecting out the desired portion of the intestine. (Lorico-Quarjiero and Chiu 1989) Windell (1978) reported a suction technique for obtaining uncontaminated faecal material from the lower large intestine. A possible source of error in this method is in the assumption that digestion and absorption are complete when the material has reached the distal end of the large intestine

Digestion is a progressive process beginning in the stomach and possibly not ending until food leaves the rectum as faeces. Most studies of digestion simply compare the protein, lipid and carbohydrate content of the faeces with that of the feed. A study on digestion in channel catfish by Smith and Lovell (1973) showed continuing digestion (and absorption) of protein during passage through each part of the gut (Table 5). The comparison of faeces collected from the rectum and from the water also points out the hazard of incomplete recovery of faecal matter being likely when collection is done from outside the gut. Most of the protein digestion occurred in the stomach, but also continued in the intestine.

Many of the methods described so far require the collection of faeces. A great variety of devices have been designed to do this, most of them producing a place with a low velocity water flow so that finely particulate faecal matter is not swept away. Research has shown significant differences between faecal composition in the water trough and in the rectum. Post (1965) designed a holding Chamber to reduce this problem by having static water around the posterior half of the fish and collecting the faeces from this water. Even collecting faeces from the rectum of fish does not solve all problems of faecal analysis because it is difficult to determine by their location in the hindgut when water reabsorption is complete.

Table 5: Apparent Digestibility of Protein by Channel Catfish

Feed	Stomach	Upper intestine	Lower intestine	Rectum	Trough
29% Protein	61.6	65.4	75.0	80.9	96.7
40% Protein	61.4	72.2	86.5	96.6	98.3

Source: Smith and Lovell, 1973

The most widely used of these techniques is the collection of faeces from the lower part of the intestine by stripping, suction or intestinal dissection. This technique generally leads to nutrients overestimation (Protein in

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particular) because of contamination of faeces with endogenous materials that would otherwise be reabsorbed before the faeces are excreted (Cho *et al.*, 1982, Hajec *et al.*, 1993b).

Use of Metabolism Chambers

Smith (1971) developed a metabolism chamber for fish which permitted separate and quantitative collection of faeces, urine and gill excretions. The fish were confined in a tube and the water surrounding the fish in the front of the chamber was separated by a rubber dam from that in the rear of the chamber. Urine was collected through a catheter into a bottle outside the chamber. The fish were force-fed daily a measured amount of feed. After 3 day preliminary period, waste collection was made for 4 or 5 days. This system permits separate and quantitative recovery of faeces, urine and gill excretions and makes possible calculation of metabolizability of feeds as well as digestibility. Nitrogen and carbon balances can also be calculated. However, the techniques of Smith (1971), where the faeces voided into the water are collected from fish immobilized in small metabolic chambers yield questionable estimates of digestibility, since the fish need to be force-fed, they often regurgitate and show negative protein and energy balances.

CHALLENGES OF DIGESTIBILITY STUDIES

When some methods for land animals are applied to fish, some challenges arise. These include the small size of fish compared to land animals. Dissolved materials in water have difficulties of decomposition such as nitrogenous compounds (NH₃). Fish excrete most of their metabolic wastes through the gills (freshwater fish excrete about 80% of their nitrogenous wastes through the gills). Also since fish are poikilothermic, body heat is dependent on the water temperature, which in turn affects the feed digestion speed and absorption

Faeces are composed of the undigested food components and the unreabsorbed residue of body origin. These residues are the remains of mucosal cells, digestive enzymes mucoproteins and other secretions released into the digestive tract by the animal, together with the residues of microflora, which inhabit the digestive tract (Nyachoti *et al.*, 1997). The faecal nitrogen not directly originating from the ingested food but from the animal itself are referred to as endogenous nitrogen gut losses (ENL). There is evidence that the amount of ENL produced by animals receiving a protein-free diet differs significantly from that of animal fed diets containing protein. In addition, several other dietary constituents (fibre, antinutritional factors) can enhance ENL (Nyachoti *et al.* 1997). For these reasons, it is reasonable to doubt the accuracy of true digestibility coefficient calculated using estimates of ENL obtained from fish fed protein-free diets.

Fish have different digestive capabilities compared to terrestrial animals, and many feedstuffs particularly cereal grains and their by products, which contain high levels of starch and fibre, are very poorly digested by carnivorous fish. The apparent digestibility of good quality protein by fish is very high. However, several factors can affect the digestibility of protein. The type of drying technique used during processing is a very important factor. A good demonstration of this is seen in blood meal (Table 4). The protein digestibility of flame-dried blood meal is very high whereas the digestibility of spray-dried blood meal is very low. The same phenomenon can occur with fishmeal (Anderson *et al.* 1993). The physical state of some ingredients may affect the digestibility of protein. For example canola meal has a rather low ADC of protein but dehulled canola meal (canola meat) has a significantly higher ADC for protein (Hilton and Slinger, 1986).

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designed a holding chamber to reduce this problem, by having static water around the posterior half of the fish and collecting the faeces from this water. Even collecting faeces from the rectum of fish does not solve all problems of faecal analysis because it is difficult to determine by their location in the hindguts when water reabsorption is complete. Thus faecal collection always includes some degree of compromise, which affects the subsequent results and the comparability with other experiments.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Continuous research is needed on the digestibility of feedstuff if fish nutrition technology is to get to the point where computer formulation of diets can be extensively used and diet ingredients interchanged on the basis of digestibility. There is the need to evaluate representative feed samples from all over the world and come up with species-specific data on digestibility. The first step in this direction would be to determine the digestibility (total and nutrient) of the individual ingredients by different species and within a species at different stages of growth. For any group of researchers, this would be a difficult task. It is therefore suggested that basic criteria be developed to determine the potential suitability of ingredients based on the proximate composition, amino acid profile, presence of growth inhibitors, fibre content as well as processability availability and cost. There are also questions on methodology that remain unanswered. At present there is not enough data to determine which inert marker is most accurate external or internal (indigenous). Also the most efficient methods of faecal collection is yet to be established. Standardization of the techniques in faecal collection, pooling of faecal collection for chemical analysis and time of collection of faeces is necessary. Some other questions that need to be answered include the effect of stress, temperature, feeling level, activity, dissolved oxygen, accumulation of metabolites on digestibility. Moreover, samples analysed must be representative of the feed ingested and the waste excreted and not subject to inaccuracies caused by leaching, handling, dilution or contamination.

In tropical Africa, a good number of cultured fish are either herbivorous or omnivorous and are known to obtain significant quantities of food from what is produced naturally in the system. It is therefore important to assess the role of microbes in digestion in such a system with a view to providing more optimal conditions for effective utilization of such food items. An aspect of digestibility in fish which has received little attention is the role of microbes. If most of these challenges are tackled we should be on the right track towards effective and sustainable fish nutrition research in aquaculture as it affects digestibility.

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